

CAREER PREFERENCE OF GRADE 12 SENIOR HIGH STUDENTS IN MINDANAO STATE UNIVERSITY - SULU

Darwisa S. Sayadi

Mindanao State University-Sulu, Capitol Site, Jolo, Sulu, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11198836>

ABSTRACT

This study was designed to determine the career preference and its influence on academic performance of grade 12 senior high school in MSU-SULU. The data was collected using a survey questionnaire that ought to answer the following questions: 1.) What are the career preferences of the grade 12 senior high school students of MSU-Sulu? 2.) What is the level of academic performance of grade 12 senior high school students of MSU-Sulu? 3.) What is the general average of grade 12 senior high school students of MSU-Sulu? 4.) Is there any significant difference on the career preference of grade 12 senior high students when grouped according to gender, socio-economic status and strand? 5.) Is there significant influence of the career preference on academic performance of grade 12 senior high students MSU-Sulu? A survey design which was mainly quantitative in nature was used in this study. A questionnaire was used in collecting data from the respondents. One hundred forty-four students participated in this study, 25% of the total population of grade 12 senior high school of MSU-SULU, were chosen from different strands such as STEM, GAS and HUMMS. SPSS Statistical Package for Social Sciences was used in calculation and to analyze the data. The study revealed that most of the students preferred courses to take are Education, Nursing, Criminology, Engineering preferably Civil engineer and Computer Engineer, and Agriculture. The academic performance of the grade 12 senior high school students with the total mean of 84.90 with verbal description of very satisfactory. Moreover, there is a significant difference in the career preference of grade 12 senior high school of MSU-Sulu when the data are grouped according to gender.

Keywords: *career preference, senior high students, Mindanao State University-Sulu*

INTRODUCTION

Career guidance is suggested among senior high schools in the Philippines. It is this stage when teenagers need guidance in the proper selection of their desired career. Where, they will arrive at the right decision considering their innate capacities, educational privilege offered to the students and other resources that society makes available for them to be more efficient and effective (DepEd, 2017).

Academic performance is the best indicator of potential for success in life; it reflects one's abilities and the qualities it takes to have an excellent academic performance are those required to be successful in life, which include consistency, determination and focus Abiola (2012). However, factors such as grades, attendance, standardized tests, and extra-curricular activities can determine the level and quality of students' academic performance Sharm (2012).

Career preference is an issue when a student is forced to take a course against his will; such a student will not feel motivated to perform well. Abdulmajid et al., (2024) as cited by Sabbaha, N. et. al, (2024) This century marks the beginning of the new trend among people and it can be widely esteemed around all ages as expressed by Sabbaha, N. et. al, (2024) cited by Mading F. et. al., (2024) and Sakili M. et. al., (2024) An ability influenced by human beings that plays a crucial role, is choosing your lifetime journey. According to Chou (2007) student's motivation to undertake their courses could be due to the recommendation of family members, friends and the easy availability of work and job security, rather than an interest in their chosen course as their profession. This could hinder their motivation to work seriously to attain a good grade. Gilman (2006) suggests that maintenance of high motivation influences psychological and social functioning, and facilitates academic performance as well as positive school perceptions and as such students will tend to perform well academically. In view of this, parents who are too demanding make students tense and this results in poor academic performance. In agreement, Mullins (2005) argues that the expectations of others and the climate which surround learners will determine their readiness to learn. This may lead to a learner's low academic performance.

Senior High school students may not be able to identify their own deficiency as far as their choices are concerned because of the interrelationship of these demographic profiles, such as age, gender, the socio - economic status of the family, the influence of the family, and their interest in choosing their career preference. Stated, that the greatest barrier among students pursuing their own career and having command over their life is the lack of in - depth knowledge of the said career. In addition, knowledge is required to make valid career preferences.

Misfit graduates are one of the considered reasons why the country has high unemployment and underemployment rate. The reasons could be either that the produced course of graduates' misfit the demand of the present economy, or the graduates do not possess the characteristics required by the industries in need. This is seen through reports that mentioned that high percentage of unemployment and

underemployment in the country is attributed to the inadequacy of skills of some of the graduates and not meeting the competencies needed by companies Rosero (2012).

One of the roles of guidance and counseling is to make it possible for an individual to see and explore his or her unlimited endowed options. Guidance counseling, one of the major services of guidance and counseling is to come up with career development program which enables guidance counselors to assist individuals to identify and learn the skills by which they can be more effective in planning for and in choosing jobs, in making effective transitions and adjustments to work and in managing their own careers and career transitions effectively.

The present global economic scenario demands one to be very serious in his/ her career planning. In this age of science and technology one should choose the right career in accordance with his/her physical as well as mental abilities, potentialities, interests, aptitudes, cognitive structuring, personality make-up and availability of resources to which he/she belongs. Students of higher education should be competent enough to choose their right career. But unfortunately, it is observed that in spite of the existence of individual differences, most students are choosing their career randomly, unintelligently, without analyzing the future orientation, psycho-physical potentialities and at the will of the parents which in turn produce unemployed graduates. In such a situation, to study the career preferences of the students becomes very important. Keeping in view the circumstances mentioned above the researcher took a study on the grade 12 students of MSU-Sulu. This study is anchored on the career preference of the senior high school in Mindanao State University-Sulu grade 12 students. The course preference has been examined in order to know the level of academic performance of the students as shaping their career in the future lies in their preference of courses to take in college.

Research Questions

The issue of the career preference of grade 12 senior high students has not been adequately addressed especially at the Mindanao State University Sulu. There is also a lack of sufficient research on ways in which career preference affects academic performance. This study sought to investigate ways in which career preference affects academic performance and its influencing force on choosing career preference of the grade 12 senior high school student in Mindanao State University-Sulu. Hence, this study is imperative to be conducted to seek answers of the following specific research questions:

1. What are the career preferences of the grade 12 senior high school students of MSU-Sulu?
2. What is the level of academic performance of grade 12 senior high school students of MSU-Sulu?
3. What is the General average of grade 12 senior high school students of MSU-Sulu?

4. Is there any significant difference on the career preference of grade 12 senior high students when grouped according to gender, socio-economic status and strand?
5. Is there significant influence of the career preference on academic performance of grade 12 senior high students MSU-Sulu?

METHODOLOGY

Research Locale

This study was conducted in MSU-Sulu utilizing the grade 12 senior high school students during the school year 2018-2019.

Sampling Method

This research utilized 25% or 144 out of 576 total population of grade 12 senior high school students as a respondent, there are seventy-two (72) males and seventy-two (72) females a total of 144 respondents. Stratified random sampling was used to select randomly samples from different strata of the population. The researcher is confident that the chosen sample is truly representative of the entire population; representatives are selected to be sampled based on their official registration of the present academic year for credible judgment.

Research Instrument

The instrument used in this study was a checklist questionnaire in the collection of data to determine the preferred career and academic performance of the grade 12 senior high students. Table 3.1 was used for analysis and interpretation of data on the performance of career preferences as cited by Sabbaha N. et. al., (2024) for their publication entitled “Effect of modular learning on the performance in biology, chemistry and physics”.

Table 3.1 was used for the analysis and interpretation of the performance of the students.

TABLE 3.1
SCALES USED FOR PERFORMANCE OF THE STUDENTS

Scales	Grades	Description
5	90-100	Outstanding
4	85-89	Very Satisfactory
3	80-79	Satisfactory
2	75-79	Fairly Satisfactory
1	Below 75	Did not meet expectation

Statistical Treatment of Data

The data was computed using Statistics Package for Social Science (SPSS). The researcher carefully prepared the data collected and necessary information to analyze. The profile data was treated statistically using frequency and percentage distribution. To determine the criteria on the significance difference when grouped according to gender, socio-economic status and strand were treated using One Way (ANOVA) One Way Analysis of Variance. And the problem of significance difference between career preference and academic performance was treated using regression.

Scope and Delimitation

This study focuses on the career preferences and its influence on the academic performance of the senior high students in Mindanao State University-Sulu. The participant of this study is delimited to the senior high students in Mindanao State University-Sulu Furthermore, the study is to be conducted only in senior high building in Mindanao State University-Sulu. The study is confined to the academic year 2018-2019.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the result and discussion of the study. The presentation of data followed the sequence according to the order of the research questions indicated in the statement of the problem or research questions.

The analysis and interpretation of data gathered from the responses of the one hundred forty-four students, of which 72 students are male and 72 females are presented in this chapter. The tables are presented in sequence according to the order of the research questions.

Table 4.1 shows that the percentage distributions of the career preferences in the different areas of discipline. Majority 25% of the 144 senior high school student-respondents preferred to take Education. 23% preferred to take Nursing. 13% preferred to take Criminology. 8% preferred to take Engineering: preferably Civil engineer and Computer Engineer. 4% preferred to take Agriculture. 2.1% preferred to take Business Administration. Equal number 1.4% preferred to take Computer Science and Hotel Restaurant Management. Equal number .7% of students preferred to take Islamic Studies, Medicine, Radiology technology, Information Technology, Pharmacy, Respiratory Therapy, and Accounting. The data indicates that the top five most preferred courses are Education, Nursing Criminology, Engineering and Agriculture.

This may be because of the common idea of students that if one wants to be employed in the future, one needs to take popular courses as stated by Saysay (2011). Smaller number of students who are fitted to Agricultural field courses which only rank 5th but not that bad, though still shows that less students are inclined to do manual work related to agriculture. This denotes that most students do not have much skills and interest when it comes to manual work related to food production, a negation to the kind of country we have: an agricultural province Sulu and an agricultural school like MSU-

Sulu. In his analysis, Watts (1996) concluded that developing countries direct their students into careers according to the country's needs. Professions have varying degrees of acceptability in different cultures which also influences an individual's career choice Kerka (2003).

TABLE 4.1
CAREER PREFERENCE OF GRADE 12 SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL
STUDENTS OF MSU-SULU

Students' preferred course	Frequency	Percentage
Education	61	42.3
Nursing	33	22.9
Criminology	19	13
Engineer	12	8.3
Agriculture	5	3.4
Business administration	3	2.0
Computer science	2	1.3
Hotel Restaurant	2	1.3
Management	1	0.7
Islamic study	1	0.7
Medicine	1	0.7
Radiology technology	1	0.7
Information technology	1	0.7
Pharmacy	1	0.7
Respiratory therapy	1	0.7
Accounting		
TOTAL	144	100

Table 4.2A shows the academic performance of grade 12 senior high school students. The general average is taken from the subjects of oral communication (English), general mathematics (Math), and earth and life science (science). The level of academic performance of grade 12 students showed that majority 29.86% of the respondent has the average of 90-100 given the verbal description outstanding, 23.61% achieved very satisfactory level of proficiency, 22.92% achieved fairly satisfactory level of proficiency, 22.22% achieved satisfactory and 1% given the verbal description did not meet expectation.

TABLE 4.2A
ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF GRADE 12 SENIOR
HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS OF MSU-SULU

Grades	Frequency	Percentage	Description
90-100	43	29.86	Outstanding
85-89	34	23.61	Very Satisfactory
80-84	32	22.22	Satisfactory
75-79	33	22.92	Fairly satisfactory

Below 75	2	1.39	Did not meet expectation
	144	100	

Legend: Below-75=Did not meet expectation; 75-79=Fairly Satisfactory; 80-84=Satisfactory; 85-89=Very Satisfactory; 90-100=Outstanding

Table 4.2B shows the general average of 84.90 indicates that the academic performance of the grade 12 senior high school students is very satisfactory.

**TABLE 4.2B
GENERAL AVERAGE GRADES OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS**

	Mean	Std. Deviation	Description
General average N=144	84.9026	5.95615	Very satisfactory

Table 4.3A shows that the F-test value (8.261) with the significant value (.005 < .05) less than the significant level of confidence. The data suggests that the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, there is a significant difference in the career preference of grade 12 senior high school of MSU-Sulu when the data are grouped according to gender.

Hypothesis:

There is no significant difference between career preference when grouped according to gender, economic status and strand of grade 12 senior high school of MSU-SULU.

**TABLE 4.3A
DIFFERENCE GROUP ACCORDING TO GENDER**

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Ho
Between Groups	78.028	1	78.028	8.261	.005	Rejected
Within Groups	1341.278	142	9.446			
Total	1419.306	143				

Table 4.3B shows the F-test (.494) with the significant value (.687 > .05), which is greater than the significant level of confidence .05. The data suggests that the null hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, there is no significant difference between career preferences when grouped according to socio-economic status of parents of grade 12 senior high school students of MSU-SULU.

**TABLE 4.3B
DIFFERENCE GROUP ACCORDING TO SOCIO ECONOMIC STATUS**

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Ho
Between Groups	14.869	3	4.956	.494	.687	Accepted
Within Groups	1404.436	140	10.032			
Total	1419.306	143				

Table 4.3C shows the significant difference between career preference of grade 12 senior high school students grouped according to their strands such as GAS, STEM and HUMMS. The F-value 2.188 with significant value .116 greater than the significant level of confidence .05 indicates no significant difference when the data are grouped according to strands.

**TABLE 4.3C
DIFFERENCE GROUPED ACCORDING TO STRANDS**

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Ho
Between Groups	42.726	2	21.363	2.188	.116	Accepted
Within Groups	1376.579	141	9.763			
Total	1419.306	143				

Table 4.4 shows the F-test (10.149) with the significant value (.002 < .05) which is less than the significant level of confidence. The data suggests that the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, there is significant influence of career preferences on academic performance of grade 12 senior high school students of MSU-Sulu. However, career preference is a good predictor of their academic performance among grade 12 senior high school students of MSU-Sulu.

Chou (2007) asserts that Career preference is a preferred choice of a course taken by a student which culminates to a specific career. A comparative lack of interest in a career can affect students' interest or commitment to a course and influence their academic performance. Abiola (2012) stressed that Academic performance is the best indicator of potential for success in life; it reflects one's abilities and the qualities it takes to have an excellent academic performance are those required to be successful in life, which include consistency, determination and focus.

Owie (2003) advances the position that the most important reason a person chooses a particular career is that the person has intrinsic interest in the field. A good match between students' learning preferences and instructor's teaching style has been demonstrated to have positive effects on students' performance Harb (2006).

Hypothesis:

There is no significant influence of career preferences on academic performance of grade 12 senior high school students of MSU-Sulu.

TABLE 4.4
INFLUENCE OF CAREER PREFERENCES ON ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Ho
1	Regression	94.674	1	.674	10.149	.002 ^b	Rejected
	Residual	1324.631	142	9.328			
	Total	1419.306	143				

a. Dependent Variable: career preference

b. Predictors: (Constant), academic performance

Conclusions

The importance of this study is to understand the influence of career preference on academic performance. With respect to course preference of students, it can be noticed that most of the preferred courses of the students are the well-known courses which include Education, nursing, and Criminology courses and the least is the promoted course of the government which are the agriculture related courses. This shows that students go with the trend on what they think is the popular course in Sulu. Consideration in choosing a course in college is the availability of possible work. It further demonstrates career preference. There are significant differences when data are grouped according to gender. Study shows that Criminology and engineering are the most favorable courses among males. However, females preferred more medical courses such as: nursing, pharmacy and respiratory therapy. While Education courses are preferred by both male and females. However, career preference is a good predictor of academic success. This means that the success of students in academics is dependent on their career preference. In addition, students should be wise in choosing their career preference since their success depends on it.

Recommendations

In the light of the findings and conclusion of the study the following recommendations are forwarded:

A. Research Agenda

1. The need to have career guidance starting from junior high school until senior high school as preparation for vocational and academic strands and preparation for college.
2. Parents should also be included in the career program development of students so that they themselves can understand and help students choose which course best fits their child's personality, interest and intellectual ability.

3. Student awareness on career preference that they want to pursue.
4. Career guidance counselors should be aware of what career that suits a student's skills and interests.
5. Motivation to those students who have the skills in agriculture to choose the career path.

B. Policy

1. The study encourages university Chancellor to come up with strategies on how they can offer programs for students' preferred courses so that students can improve on their academic performance.
2. The admission office ought to intervene when students are being enrolled to ensure they are grilled to find out if they have chosen a course of choice and if the university offers the course.
3. Mandatory training of career guidance counseling teachers and establishing counseling cells in every school year for the upcoming senior high school students to deal with this problem.
4. School administrators provide both financial and material to enable the schools to implement career guidance activities in schools.
5. Collaborative effort of the school administrations, guidance counselors and parents should also be made to come up with better career plans for every individual student.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher hereby declares that an informed consent was obtained from the respondents of the study. The survey was conducted to gather pertinent data in research. A written permission and communication letter was initially addressed to the coordinator of the senior high school at MSU-SULU. Upon the approval, the researcher personally administered the questionnaire. The researcher used the time allotted for vacant seats to avoid distractions of class discussions. The researcher instructed the students how to answer the questionnaire and given enough time to answer the questions, and soon the respondents had already done, then the researcher retrieved the necessary information. In addition, the researchers assure that the information gathered from respondents are kept confidential. Plagiarism was strictly observed throughout the research process.

Acknowledgements

The researcher would like to express her sincere appreciation and heartfelt gratitude to all those who in one way or another eagerly supported and helped her in making this research possible. To the Senior High Coordinator, the teachers and students of grade 12 Senior High School for their support to the success of the study. To **Ms. Honeylaine S. Kadil**, the researcher sincerely appreciated for sharing her knowledge and insight. Special thanks particularly to the following person:

Dr. Magna Anissa A. Hayudini, chairperson of defense panel, for her constructive

comments and suggestions;

Dr. Madeline A. Tan, her adviser, for providing invaluable insights and suggestions. Likewise, for her constant effort in directing the course of the research work especially her persistence in encouraging the writer to keep on;

Dr. Rafael A. Regellana, critic of defense panel, his constructive comments and suggestions;

Dr. Abdurajik S. Dansalan, panelist for his helpful suggestions and encouragements.

Dr. Said Abdurajak, her panelist for his constructive suggestions especially in statistics to make this study more significant.

Special thanks are also extended to the following precious person TRULY HER INSPIRATION:

To her children: **Rayyana, Rizqkhan, Rawan Refa and Rofaya Rich**, for their emotional support and inspiration during her most difficult times while undertaking this study.

Lastly, to her husband **Nurhartam N. Sayadi**, for his unconditional love, understanding, constant encouragement, and especially for his financial support. Furthermore, for the quality time he spent with his family despite of busy workloads.

Most of all, thanks to **ALMIGHTY ALLAH**, whose guidance and blessings gave the researcher good health, courage, perseverance and determination to finish the research work.

REFERENCES

- Abdulmajid, B. P., Sabbaha, N. A., Kamlon, B. A., Tolentino, L. H., Alih, D. R. S., Jhun, F. J., & Hadjula, T. F. (2024). SOCIAL MEDIA EXPOSURE: ITS EFFECT ON THE PERFORMANCE IN MATHEMATICS OF GENERAL ACADEMIC STRAND STUDENTS IN A UNIVERSITY IN SULU, SOUTHERN PHILIPPINES. *Ignatian International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research*, 2(5), 622–631. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11148259>
- Abiola O (2012). *Academic performance the best indicator of potential for success in life*. Retrieved from: <http://www.fogs.com/articles/academic-performance-the-bestindicator-of-potential-for-success-in-life-1622>. Accessed 12 May 2014.
- Chou, M. H. & Lee, L.C. (2007). *Initial formation of nursing philosophies following fundamental clinical practice: The experience of Male Nursing Students*. *Journal of Nursing Research*, 15(2), 127–137.
- Gilman, R., & Anderman, E. M. (2006). *The relationship between relative levels of motivation, intrapersonal, interpersonal and academic functioning among older adolescents*. *Journal of School Psychology*. Vol. 44: 375-391.
- Harb, N., & El-Shaarawi, A. (2006). *Factors affecting Student performance*. Munich Personal RePEc Archive Paper No. 13621.
- Kerka, 2000; Bandura, .Barbaranelli, Caprara & Pastorelli, 2001; McQuaid & Bond, 2003).
- Mading, F. A. E. B., Sahali, B. G., Hashim, A.-H. I., Aziz, K. M., Hail, J. G., Kuyong, N. A., Salialam, A. L., Aming, A. R. H., Balla, F. S. J., Jailani, A. B., Muhadja, N. B., Jaafar, A.-. sharif H., Jaafar, S. H., Asaali, N. K., Muhalim, B. S., Abdulmajid, B. P., & Sabbaha, N. A. (2024). TECHNOLOGY - MEDIATED INSTRUCTION'S CHALLENGES: ITS EFFECT

- TO ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE AMONG SCIENCE TECHNOLOGY ENGINEERING MATHEMATICS STUDENTS IN A UNIVERSITY IN SULU, SOUTHERN PHILIPPINES. *Ignatian International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research*, 2(5), 354–362. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11114423>
- Mullins, L. J. (2005). *Management and Organizational Behavior*. 7th ed. London: Financial Times Prentice Hall.
- Owie, I. (2003). *Teaching, a priori or a posteriori decision: A preliminary analysis of effective impact*, *African Journal of Studies in Education*; 1, 21–29.
- Rosero, Earl Victor . “*Why many fresh college grads don't get hired, according to survey of managers*”, *GMA News*
<http://www.gmanetwork.com/news/story/250239/economy/business/why-many-fresh-collegegrads-don-t-get-hired-according-to-survey-of-managers>. March 3, 2012
- Sabbaha, N. A. (2024). ACADEMIC TENACITY IN SCIENCE AMONG STUDENTS IN PRIVATE SCHOOL IN INDANAN SULU, SOUTHERN PHILIPPINES. *Ignatian International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research*, 2(5), 717–724. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11174579>
- Sabbaha, N. A., Abbang, N. M., Julpikal, N. H., Jailani, A. B., Muhalim, B. S., Abuhasil, S. M., Assali, N. K., Nadar, A. A., Sali Alam, A. L., Sayadi, D. S., & Cabajon, H. A. (2024). Effect of Modular Learning On Performance in Biology, Chemistry and Physics of General Science Students of Mindanao State University-Sulu. *Ignatian International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research*, 2(4), 1573–1585. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11077327>
- Sakili, M. H., Sabbaha, N. A., Abdulmajid, B. P., Bahari, N. A., Amirul, M. G., Anni, A. H., & Hadjula, T. F. (2024). MODULAR DISTANCE LEARNING APPROACH: ITS EFFECT ON STUDENTS' PERFORMANCE IN PRE-CALCULUS. *Ignatian International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research*, 2(5), 997–1011. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11180593>
- Saysay, Karen-Lyn. (2011). *A qualitative study on Pilipino Americans students relative to their high school success and career choices*. Published Dissertation. Faculty of the USC Rossier School of Education, University of Southern California.
- Sharm (2012). *Meaning of academic performance*. Retrieved from: [https://www.google.com/search?q=Sharm+\(2012\).+Meaning+of+academic+performance.&rlz=1C1GCEA_enRO1052PH1059&oq=Sharm++++\(2012\).++Meaning++of++academic++performance.&gs_lcrp=EgZjaHJvbWUyBggAEEUYOTIHCAEQIRigATIHCAlQIRigAdlBBzM2MmowajeoAgiwAgE&sourceid=chrome&ie=UTF-8](https://www.google.com/search?q=Sharm+(2012).+Meaning+of+academic+performance.&rlz=1C1GCEA_enRO1052PH1059&oq=Sharm++++(2012).++Meaning++of++academic++performance.&gs_lcrp=EgZjaHJvbWUyBggAEEUYOTIHCAEQIRigATIHCAlQIRigAdlBBzM2MmowajeoAgiwAgE&sourceid=chrome&ie=UTF-8)
- Watts, A. G. (1996). *A framework for comparing careers guidance systems in different countries*. *Educational and Vocational Guidance Bulletin*, 55, 1-7.